

FEATURES OF INTEGRATED LEARNING

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Abstract: The article analyzes the features of integrated teaching of academic disciplines and makes recommendations.

Keywords: science, education, integration, knowledge, quality, international, experience, program, strategy, basis, learning, initial, process.

The fourth direction of the “New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan” is the implementation of quality education. At the same time, the tasks of developing human capital through quality education and upbringing and pursuing a fair social policy have been identified. Therefore, the formation of human capital, that is, the mental capacity of the individual, begins with primary education, and it is known that the ability to justice is also formed in the individual at this stage of education it is in this respect that quality primary education plays an important role in ensuring the performance of tasks. Quality education is the process of achieving the expected effectiveness of the educational process by organizing it on the basis of national education and international education programs. This means achieving the quality of education as a result of the implementation of the set and tasks. The most important issue is the mastery of the teaching materials by the learners, and the quality of education is assessed accordingly.

In this regard, there are many foundations for the organization and implementation of quality primary education. One of them is the integrated learning process. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 “On measures to develop science and education in the new period of development of Uzbekistan” sets the task of “integrated teaching of subjects in secondary schools”.

Also, the “State Education Standard for General Secondary Education” approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 6, 2017 No 187 states that one of the main tasks of general secondary education is “ensuring effective integration of education, science and industry”. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 14, 2021 “On measures to further improve the activities of the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of Tashkent region” sets the following tasks: ensuring the integration of information and communication educational technologies;

Use of TIMS, PIRLS and STEAM standards in the teaching process and scientific research, etc.

All this shows that the study of the pedagogical problem of integrative teaching of primary education is relevant. In this regard, we draw your attention to the analysis of important issues of integrated learning.

1. The content of integration. The word “integration” is derived from the Latin “integerara” and means “to fill, create, restore commonality”. The Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language states: “Integration is the joining, merging and rounding of individual parts or elements into a whole”. The meanings of addition, wholeness, and rounding in this definition are taken as pedagogical content

The National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan defines the concept of integration as follows:

- 1) represents the state of interdependence of certain parts and functions of a system or organism and the process leading to such a state;
- 2) the process of convergence and interaction of disciplines;
- 3) mutual coordination and integration of the economies of two or more countries. The second of these definitions of the term integration refers to the meaning applied directly to the process of education and upbringing

This concept as a term refers to the interdependence, interdependence, and harmony of an event or phenomenon. It is this definition that has been adopted in our study as the basis for the concept of integration.

The integration factor has recently been widely used in all spheres of social life. It is therefore advisable to pay attention to the following aspects of integration:

- 1) understand the interrelationship of events and phenomena;
- 2) understanding of the interdependence of tools and methods in the process of work;
- 3) rational use of the principles of integration in solving problems.

Such an approach is divided into the ability to solve problems and develop new developments using the capabilities of the integration factor. Thus, the following two functions of the integration factor should be considered

a) integration orientation. This involves determining a single correct conclusion based on the interdependence of infinite and many small parts that make up information, their integrity, integrity;

b) types of integration tasks. This means that when solving a problem, the causes of the problem are studied in harmony, and based on them, solutions to the problem are developed.

It should be noted that the following three principles play an important role in the integration factor:

- dependence;
- relevance;
- harmony

An integration process and factor based on such principles requires a balanced use of the potential of the pros and cons of the issue in achieving the goal.

Positive and negative aspects are observed in the integration factor. Its positive aspect is that traditional approaches are updated on the basis of a new approach, while its negative aspect is sometimes reflected in the change in the methods of the traditional approaches experienced.

1. Therefore, when the integration factor is applied to the teaching process, it is expedient to focus on maintaining the tried and tested methods of the traditional approach, while creating a new approach. This is especially important in the judicious use of the integration factor in the teaching process.

2. Features of integrated learning. In pedagogical dictionaries, the concept of "integrated teaching" is used in the sense of connection and interdependence. In this sense, the concept of "integrated learning" means "ensuring consistency in the content of education."

In this regard, according to our definition, integrated learning is a process of organizing the process of education and upbringing in an interconnected, interconnected and harmonious way, and achieving its expected results. If these issues are understood and the

ability of primary school teachers to apply them in practice is achieved, the opportunities to achieve the effectiveness of education and upbringing will expand.

It should be noted that the issue of training plays an important role here. Teaching is an internal connection between the purpose, content, form, methods and techniques that are subject to certain laws and applied to the educational process in accordance with the general philosophical methodology. As a result of training, the learner is provided with the necessary knowledge and is prepared for the next stage of education in terms of knowledge, skills and qualifications.

In organizing the learning process, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

selection of convenient, easy and effective teaching methods;

relying on science-based and modern teaching technology:

based on theoretically, methodologically and practically sound information and data set for teaching.

It should be noted that these features, which are specific to the teaching process, are also specific to the content of integrated teaching.

It is known that several types and methods of teaching are currently in use at the present stage. The following types of teaching are distinguished by pedagogical experien

1) teaching based on tradition and perseverance;

2) developmental training;

3) problem-based learning;

4) program training, etc.

The characteristics of these types of teaching are integrated into the integrated learning process

The following teaching methods are noteworthy:

1) effective teaching method;

2) creative teaching method;

3) emotional-value teaching method, etc.

There are opportunities to use these methods of experiential learning in defining the content of integrated learning.

Thus, the features of integrated teaching of academic disciplines are an important phenomenon in theory and practice. The main goal is to teach disciplines in an interconnected, interdependent and harmonious way.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Will firmly pursue the path of democratic reforms on the basis of the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan. // "Yangi O'zbekiston" newspaper, November 7, 2021 issue.

2. Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language. 2 volumes. 1-tom.-M., 1981. 330-b. 3. National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. 4-vol.-T., 2001. 179-p.

4. Pedagogical encyclopedia. 1-vol.-T., 2012. 70-p.

5. Abduraxmonov O. Integration of science, education and production.-T.: "Science and technology". 2014

6. Hasanboev J., Turakulov H., Haydarov M., Hasanboeva O., Usmonov N. Annotated dictionary of pedagogy.-T.: "Science and technology" 2009. 183-p.

7. Bordovskaya N.V., Rean A.A. Pedago